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Practical Research on the Lifelong Learning Model of the Largest Scientific Research Institution in China

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ABSTRACT

In the era of knowledge economy, the time cycle of knowledge updating is shortened to 2~3 years. The development of the fourth research paradigm puts forward new requirements for big data and computing ability of researchers. As the highest academic institution of Natural Science in China, the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) has more than 70,000 scientists who distributed in 23 provinces and cities. How to meet the lifelong learning needs of the distributed researchers has become the focus in recent years. CAS has practiced for 5years in keeping up with the needs of scientists since 2014. Finally CAS proposed a lifelong learning model and built lifelong learning environment. All kinds of learning data indicate that this learning model is effective and sustainable.

1 INTRODUCTION

CAS was established on November 1, 1949, in Beijing, where it is headquartered. CAS is China's largest comprehensive R&D organization in the natural sciences and high technology. CAS is the linchpin of China's drive to explore and harness high technology and the natural sciences for the benefit of China and the world. CAS brings together scientists and engineers from China and around the world to address both theoretical and applied problems using world-class scientific and management approaches. CAS comprises more than 100 research institutes which are located in

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23 provinces and autonomous regions across China. These institutions are home to more than 100 national key labs and engineering centres as well as nearly 200 CAS key labs and engineering centers. Altogether, CAS comprises 1,000 sites and stations across the country. CAS Headquarters in Beijing manages the entire organization under the leadership of the CAS president. CAS has a staff of 70,023, including about 58,697 professional researchers. With the rapid development of information technology CAS is facing the challenge about how to satisfy the lifelong learning needs of 70,000 researchers who are distributed across China.^[1]

The main objective of this proposal is to explore effective lifelong learning models and to create a special learning environment that is in line with the lifelong learning needs of researchers using advanced technologies. The main work includes the following 3 aspects: 1) study of various effective Lifelong learning model such as MOOC etc. 2) through online survey, analysis of CAS scientists' lifelong learning needs; 3) Practices on the lifelong learning model of scientists including study all kinds of learning resources that CAS scientists need and formulate effective assessment methods and assessment mechanisms and construct a continuing education environment that is in line with the lifelong learning of CAS scientists.

1.1 The development of knowledge updating

According to the study launched by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), information technology has brought the high speed development to human knowledge. In 18th Century, the time cycle of knowledge updating is about 80 to 90 years, from nineteenth Century to early 20th Century, it's been reduced to 30 years, the last century 60~70's, the general time cycle of knowledge updating is about 5 to 10 years, and in the 80~90's of last century, the time has been shortened to 5 years, entered the new century, the time cycle of most disciplines has been shortened to 2~3 years.^[2] With the development of Internet, 90% of the data of human beings are generated in the first two years. The IDC report shows that by 2020, the total number of global data will exceed 40ZB (equivalent to 4 trillion GB).^[3]

1.2 The learning needs the fourth scientific paradigm proposes^[4]

Jim Gray who received the ACM A.M. Turing Award in 1998 put forward that scientific paradigms could be categorized in four models. Thousand years ago science was empirical. Last few hundred years theoretical branch occurred that scientists did their work through using models and generalizations. When it came to last few decades scientists carried research by simulating complex phenomena that was called a computational branch. Today we meet the fourth science paradigm that was named data-intensive scientific discovery. It was developed in the big data era. New scientific paradigm poses challenges on today's scientists. Today's scientists must catch up with the development of new technology and grasp a few kinds of skills such as the ability of analysis of big data and cloud computing. Most scientists should know how to integrate heterogeneous data and how to deal with mass data and many kinds of domain algorithm and how to visualize the research conclusion. At the same time big data improve the development of interdisciplinary. It means that

scientists should know more subjects beyond their only major. Only by doing so can scientists discovery new knowledge.

1.3 The rapid development of information technology changes learning model

With the development of information technology and multimedia technology our learning model changes accordingly. In 1989 University of Phoenix launched its online program [5]. The term of open educational resources (OER) was firstly coined at UNESCO's 2002Forum [6]. The organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) defines OER as “digitized materials offered freely and openly for educators, students, and self-learners to use and reuse for teaching, learning and research”. There is no universal usage of open file formats in OER. The term OER describes publicly accessible materials and resources for any user to use, re-mix, improve and redistribute under some licenses. Massachusetts Institute of technology (MIT) announced OpenCourseWare on April 4, 2001[7]. Under this project MIT put all of the educational materials from its undergraduate- and graduate-level courses online, freely and openly available to anyone, anywhere. MIT OpenCourseWare is a large-scale, web-based publication of MIT course materials. Khan Academy is non-profit educational organization created in 2006 by educator Salman Khan with a goal of creating a set of online tools that help educate students [8]. The organization produces short lectures in the form of YouTube videos. The videos show a recording of drawings on an electronic blackboard, which are similar to the style of a teacher giving a lecture. Its website also includes supplementary practice exercises and materials for educators. David M. Penrose (aka the One Minute Professor), an independent instructional designer and eLearning consultant, has articulated the process for creating microlectures[9]. Microlecture is used to refer to actual instructional content that is formatted for online and mobile learning content using a constructivist approach.

Fig.1. MOOCs

Fig. 2. Researchers and managers

According to The New York Times, 2012 became “the year of the MOOC” as several well-financed providers, associated with top universities, emerged, including Coursera, Udacity, and edX. A massive open online course (MOOC) is an online course aimed at unlimited participation and open access via the web. In addition to traditional materials such as lectures, readings, and problem sets, many MOOCs provide interactive user forums to support community interactions among students, professors, and teaching assistants [10]. Moocs as shown in Fig. 1.

2 THE SCIENTISTS' LIFELONG LEARNING NEEDS

The fourth scientific paradigm proposes new challenges on the researchers. In consideration of the training needs of CAS we also must understand the researchers' personal lifelong learning needs. We gathered the researchers' learning needs mainly through questionnaire and interview. We mainly do two kinds of questionnaire. Firstly CAS launches a training need survey every 5 years. This kind of survey covers all the workers of CAS. The investigation issues focus on content needs and learning methods. Secondly every research institute carries out investigation among its own staff every year. The second type of survey focuses on subject learning needs and expected teacher. The results of the two types of survey could give us enough data to analyze the researchers' needs thoroughly. In this research we mainly analyze the data form the survey that carried out among all the researchers in 2014. This survey was named "A questionnaire on the needs of continuing education and training in CAS". A sampling survey among 872 researchers was carried out. According to the proportion of different title levels the training superintendent of HR Department decided the list who took part in the survey. The survey was executed from March to June in 2014.

2.1 More working time less learning time

The 872 researchers that took part in this survey are from 117 scientific institutes. Among them, there are 233 science and technology managers and 639 scientific researchers. As shown in *Fig. 2*. For the purpose of understanding the learning needs of various post we sampled 255 junior researchers and 338 middle level researchers and 279 senior researchers. As shown in *Fig. 3*.

Fig. 3. Levels of researchers

Fig. 4. Working time statistics

We try to know the researchers' learning time by the question "how long time do you engage in researching work every day". 72% of the Interviewee work more than 9 hours a day. 95% of the Interviewee work more than 8 hours a day. Even 32% of the Interviewee work more than 10 hours a day. These results show that work takes the researchers much time every day that they could not have enough time to learn. We need to think about how to balance work and study time. As shown in *Fig. 4*.

2.2 The effective training way

As the learning time was so limited we want to know the most effective way of training. 324 researchers thought it is more effective to study while working. 190 interviewees believed that the best way is to get away from the job and concentrate on learning for a while. 358 researchers regarded all kinds of lectures, visits and

exchanges as the best way to meet their learning needs. It means that 41% of the interviewees prefer to visit and interact with each other. As shown in *Fig. 5*.

Fig. 5. Effective training way

Fig. 6. Learning content needs

2.3 The learning content needs

Furthermore we want to know what kinds of learning content the scientists needed to improve their work. The options for this problem included management ability, frontier knowledge, interdisciplinary knowledge, scientific research ability, and scientific literacy. While CAS is engaged in almost fields in natural science the researchers' needs were distributed in many fields. 37% of the researchers wanted to learn more knowledge about scientific management. 31% of the interviewees needed to know more about frontier knowledge and interdisciplinary content. We can infer that these researchers were interested in cross field. 22% researchers thought they need to improve their research ability. Finally there were 91 researchers want to improve their scientific literacy. This means that 10% of the interviewees wanted to understand general knowledge beyond their own research fields. As shown in *Fig. 6*.

2.4 Other personal learning needs

For getting more details of personal learning needs we design some subjective questions. One question is "what service do you want the institute to provide you according to your career planning and development." Mostly every researcher wrote down their own needs. We sorted these answers into three major aspects.

(1) Strengthening continuing education support through policy

Many researchers advised CAS put forward independent policy about continuing education. There are four points in details. Firstly CAS should design all the continuing education work from Top-level to improve training work Standardized and systematized. Secondly CAS was supposed to ensure learning time for every researcher to resolve the conflict between learning time and work time. Thirdly CAS should provide more continuing education opportunity such as studying abroad or exchanging abroad. Finally CAS was supposed to ask every institute to set up funds to support continuing education and encourage every researcher to learn.

(2) Building learning platform to promote the sharing of resources

Some researchers suggested building learning platform to promote the sharing of resources. This can solve many problems by a learning platform. First of all every researcher can learn any time anywhere by learning the resources online. Many scientists who major in the same field often are distributed across China. How could

they exchange each other's ideas effectively and share knowledge quickly? Through a learning platform many researchers can interactive effectively and even develop deep cooperation.

(3) Individualized and problem-based learning

As mentioned above, the interviewees wanted six kinds of learning content. It included research ability, interdisciplinary, information literacy, scientific literacy, management ability and industrialization. Which way do the researchers prefer to get these knowledge and ability? Scientists put forward three learning modes. The first was to provide training service for various kinds of post, and provide corresponding training content according to the levels of posts. Second was to provide individual learning service. The third was to concentrate on the research focus to improve the occurrence of effective learning through the problem oriented learning model.

3 PRACTICAL RESEARCHES ON THE LIFELONG LEARNING MODE

The continuing educational resources CAS provided before 2014 were consisted of training classes. This kind of training mode can fix the learning needs about frontier knowledge and management ability effectively. In a training class the participants can exchange face to face. It was proved that training class is an effective way.

Under the fourth scientific paradigm scientists should update their knowledge especially the knowledge about big data and cloud computing. And scientists may develop more and more cooperation between similar or different subject. How to update scientists' knowledge effectively? Training class is an expensive model. The learning materials cannot be stored and shared widely while a training class can only accept no more than one hundred participants one time. And we cannot gather all the learning data. While the period training class ends the learning ends.

3.1 Drafting policy to ensure the learning time for every scientist

In order to guarantee the time for every researcher to study, CAS drafts a policy named "Measures for the registration and management of continuing education and training time". It claims that the scientists have the right and obligation to receive continuing education and training, and the institutes have the duty to carry out continuing education and training. In this policy a scientist's learning time should be up to 100 hours, and the leaders' learning time should not be less than 110 hours every year. Scientist's study time is related to job promotion and annual assessment. This regulation is made to protect scientist's learning rights.

3.2 Establishing training implementation system

CAS has established a training implementation system for every kind of post. CAS is responsible for the training of the strategic management. Various bureaus are responsible for various special management training. The Institute is mainly responsible for scientific and technical professional training for researchers. The Continuing education bases under CAS are responsible for the integration of training in the field of discipline. The Continuing education bases under the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security of China are responsible for professional and technical training for all of the scientists. Based on our practices we carried out

theoretical research to standardize the training process for all the institutes mentioned above. The standardized training process includes six phases including survey, plan, implement, resource, assessment and statistical analysis.

3.3 Developing many kinds of training resources to meet individualized needs

The training implementation system has clearly defined the training responsibilities of all institutes. Under this training implementation frame we have carried out further work to specialize training content and methods.

(1) Building competitive training classes

The training class is implemented offline. It focuses on the frontier knowledge and management ability. We further subdivide training classes into short term special technical classes, professional technical high research classes, post training, academic conferences and academic lectures to meet every post's learning needs. CAS has implemented more than 5000 classes every year. In addition we have increased support for studying abroad, and supported researchers to carry out short-term academic exchanges abroad.

(2) Online courseware

Fig. 7. Science micro course

Fig. 8. Three-part- Screen Course

CAS builds science microcourses and three-part-separated Screen Web Course to update scientists' knowledge. The length of each science micro course is less than 20 minutes, which is taught by CAS's researcher. A science micro course can be a series of short videos or only one short video. We divide the series into two category, scientific professional research micro courses and science popularization micro courses. The scientific professional micro courses are produced for scientist to improve major research ability while the science popularization micro courses are produced to promote interdisciplinary. In addition, we have invited the academicians to tell the scientific story to develop micro course to meet the needs of the scientific spirit. Based on the excellent training classes offline we build three-part-separated Screen Web Course. This kind of web course lasts for 1 to 3 hours and it can explain professional knowledge systematically. Science micro courses as shown in Fig. 7. Three-part-separated Screen Web Course as shown in Fig. 8.

(3) Teacher database

Through building teacher database we guarantee the quality of courseware. We set up a variety of evaluation indicators to select better teachers and provide learning opportunity to improve teacher's teaching skills. As shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Teacher Database

3.4 Organizing training assessment to improve the training work

In order to ensure the effect of the continuing education, CAS has developed a series of assessment indicators. This assessment indicator system mainly includes organization guarantee, policy, curriculum system, training need analysis, plan making, training implementation, and project evaluation, training funds, training materials, training teachers and resources sharing. CAS evaluates every institution's outputs of training work each year through data extraction and Interview.

3.5 Building CASmooc eLearning system and recording big learning data

Now we have many kinds of continuing education resources such as training classes and online courseware and teacher information distributed in every research institute of CAS. And we have set up a standard training process. Based on all the work mentioned above we build CASmooc. In 2016, CASmooc was officially launched online to provide learning service for every scientist anytime anywhere and record every researcher's learning data. The CASmooc platform's function mainly consists of three parts including management, learning and resource sharing. Its management function means it can support every institute implement the total continuing education. Its learning function means it serves every scientist in online learning and registering training class and taking part in surveys. Every learner can interact with others while learning the same courseware and participating in the same class. In order to ensure the authenticity of the learning data, every scientist must use his real name on CASmooc. It supports every institute determine whether open their resources or not autonomously. We developed CASmooc applications on android and IOS which supports offline learning. While scientist takes part in a training class he can record his learning data by scanning QR code. Scientist also can record learning data anytime anywhere by using mobile terminal. CASmooc supports live course and it reduces the cost of participating in a training class.

4 RESULTS

4.1 The Lifelong Learning Model of CAS

Since 2014, CAS has been initially drafted "Measures for the registration and management of continuing education and training time", established the continuing education implemented system, developed a variety of training resources, and organized training assessment work several times. CAS has formed its effective life-long learning mode for researchers. As shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Lifelong learning model

Through the comparison of the learning data in 2014 and 2017, we can see that our lifelong learning model is effective and has gained some achievements.

4.2 The learning data comparison

Through analysing the learning data in 2014 and 2017 we can see there are three changes. Firstly there has been a big increase in the learning data and the learning data is more detailed. Secondly the scope of learning data statistics becomes larger. The third is to set up a study file for each scientist. In 2014, CAS held 2224 training classes and there are 146 thousand trainees involved. In 2017, CAS held 5765 training classes and there are 321 thousand trainees attended. 250 thousand scientists are trained outside CAS in 2017 while there is no record about this data in 2014. The learning data mainly included the training classes held in CAS in 2014. The learning data included both in CAS and out of CAS, and these data was identified as offline learning data or online learning data in 2017. In 2017 the learning data was 5415868.9 hours, of which the online learning data was 621966.2 hours and the offline learning data was 4793902.7 hours. The internal learning data was 2387246.1 hours, and the external learning data was 3028622.8 hours.

4.3 Feedback

A questionnaire survey was carried out in 2016 while CASmoooc has been running for half a year. More than 100 researchers participated. 95% of the users thought that CASmoooc is beautiful and easily used. And later we have an interview with 20 researchers from 8 research institutes in Wuhan branch to get user's suggestions. They suggested making more science micro - courseware to meet fragmented learning needs. They suggested that sum up all kinds of success experience in using CASmoooc and carry out various exchanges to share experiences to improve the use of CASmoooc. They suggested that policy incentives combine with the construction of high quality resources and change passive learning into active learning.

5 CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

After more than 5 years of exploration, CAS has initially established a life-long learning model for researchers. All kinds of feedback data indicate that CAS has achieved some achievements. But with the development of information technology, especially the development of big data technology and the scale of open resources, CAS in the future will still take efforts to promote deep learning and build sharable

learning environment. We plan to further describe the resources, and use knowledge map and ontology to integrate resources at the semantic level so as to better meet the individualized learning needs of scientists^[11]. We will deepen the level of service, from the Institute to the laboratory, eventually to person. By analysing the big learning data, we have a plan to build model for every scientist. Using a variety of algorithms to realize the personalized recommendation of learning resources and improve the learning experience of users. On the basis of the continuing education network of CAS, we will share our resources with various scientific research institutions all over the world to promote the exchange of disciplines and cooperation.

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